

AI-Powered Spectrum Sensing Capabilities for Future Networks Beyond 5G

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Abstract— The wide spread of wireless devices and services has significantly increased the demand for radio spectrum. This leads to congestion, especially in urban areas where many users and devices compete for the same radio frequency bandwidths. Improving the efficiency of spectrum allocation through new technologies and AI algorithms to better optimise radio resource allocation for increased scalability and improved performance is crucial. This paper presents the design and development of an AI framework for spectrum sensing that can be applied to B5G technologies. From the obtained results, we can conclude that the developed AI algorithm ensures a high level of performance achieving an accuracy of 97,1% when classifying 4G and NR 5G communications.

Keywords—spectrum sensing, radio sensing, Artificial Intelligence, Beyond 5G technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communications have become an integral part of our lives. The way people transmit their information is mainly based on wireless communication technologies, without which mobility and easy access to information anywhere would be impossible. Over the past decade, we have witnessed an immense growth in wireless communication protocols and applications that are used by billions of people every day at home and at work. Regardless of the communication mechanism, the modulation used, the hardware required, all these revolutionary technologies share the same communication, physical medium; the same limited resource called radio frequency spectrum. From IoT devices to mobile communications, millions of sensors and devices are competing for the same radio resource.

The proliferation of wireless devices and services has significantly increased the demand for radio spectrum. This leads to congestion, especially in urban areas where many users and devices compete for the same radio frequency bandwidths. As the demand for wireless communications continues to grow, future developments may include exploring higher frequency bands (such as millimetre waves) with greater costs or increasing the efficiency of spectrum allocation through new technologies and AI algorithms to better optimise radio resource allocation increasing scalability and improve performance.

Radio Sensing, commonly referred to as Spectrum Sensing (SS), is an advanced field that incorporates a comprehensive range of methodologies dedicated to understanding and optimising the use of the Radio Frequency (RF) spectrum. Initially, the application of radio frequency sensing was predominantly met in the military sector. Today, spectrum sensing is recognized as an encompassing term that defines an ensemble of techniques for the capture, recording, and analysis of radio frequency waves. These techniques are used in numerous applications to identify radio communications and use this information for radio channel optimization and allocation. Such identifications can be systematically classified using AI (Artificial Intelligence) algorithms according to the specific objectives, which represents a key development in the use of radio detection technologies and radio resource optimisation.

Figure 1 presents a map of the various sectors and applications where spectrum sensing plays a significant role. In Cognitive Radio (CR), spectrum sensing is crucial for gathering spectrum information, enabling dynamic spectrum access and an enhanced understanding of efficient radio spectrum resource use. for IoT radio channel resource optimization based on AI.

Fig. 1. Radio-sensing domains of application.

Other applications that make use of spectrum sensing technologies include: large scale high density IoT applications, public and road safety, UAVs, e-Health, location and positioning and radio resource allocation in B5G technologies. This overview underscores the integral role of radio sensing in advancing technology and improving operational radio efficiency and increase the performance level. This paper is a continuation of our previous work [1], [2] related to spectrums sensing algorithms

The paper is organised as follows: a brief introduction is given first that includes the motivation behind this work, followed by Section II, which describes the main challenges of radio spectrum sensing problems. In Section III, the spectrum sensing paradigm for B5G communications is introduced and discussed. Section IV presents the novel radio sensing framework that integrates advanced AI algorithms. The obtained experimental results are discussed in Section V. The paper ends with a conclusion section that centralized the main contribution of this paper.

II. SPECTRUM SENSING CHALLENGES

Recently, research in spectrum sensing has led to the capability of identifying specific modulations or wireless communication protocols, enhancing the detection capabilities past radio channel occupancy [1]. Classical methods for achieving this have relied on likelihood-based approaches, which compute the probability that a received signal matches one or multiple known radio signal profiles from specific modulation classes or communication protocols. While these methods can generate theoretically ideal outcomes, their practical application is limited by significant computational inefficiency and hardware implementation challenges.

In response to these limitations, the research community has moved towards more practical, feature-based approaches [2]. These methods predominantly harness machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) algorithms to classify received signal. The primary challenge with feature-based methods lies in the preprocessing stage, where the received signal must be processed to extract features that are both distinctive and computationally manageable by the processing system.

In [3] and [4] Tim O'Shea et al. propose the use of In phase and Quadrature (I/Q) complex radio signal samples along with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to identify and classify 24 distinct modulation classes using a dataset from DeepSig [5]. Their findings show that I/Q samples, while posing no computational challenges, can't generate discriminative features of a radio signal at low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) values, especially for high order digital modulations such as 16/32PSK, 64/128/256QAM, as the authors report a detection accuracy of 80% only for SNR values above 10 dB SNR. Using the same dataset, Rajendran et al. [6] show that preprocessing the I/Q complex samples into Amplitude and Phase or Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) series, while using a Long Short Time Memory network can bring detection improvements, their reported accuracy reaching to 90% for SNR values above 0 dB. In [7], M. Zhang et al. introduce a novel strategy for addressing the issue of radio modulation detection and classification by proposing the use of a CNN that processes inputs derived from time-frequency domain graphical representations. These

representations are generated by applying the Choi-Williams distribution (CWD) [8] to the analyzed radio signals, followed by subsequent processing steps. Their reports show accuracy values of 90% for SNR values ranging from -2 dB to 8 dB.

Tang et al. in [9] adopt the AlexNet [10] neural network paired with transfer learning to address the modulation classification challenge. Their approach involves processing the signals fed into the CNN as graphical representations derived from constellation diagrams. To enhance the classification accuracy, they further refine these diagrams by encoding the density of the points with a color gradient. This technique visually differentiates the number of symbols present, and by extension, the modulation order (e.g., QPSK with 4 symbols, 16QAM with 16 symbols, 32QAM with 32 symbols). Their method showed an improvement for detection at low SNR values reaching 80% accuracy at -4 dB SNR.

The capabilities of spectrum sensing go beyond modulation detection and are also related to radio device identification or fingerprinting. Radio device identification techniques assume that each radio device has a unique fingerprint resulting from its hardware implementation. Thus, even if two or more radio devices use the same modulation type, the same communication protocol and transmit the same data packet, each radio transmission will have unique characteristics, which can be highlighted using a Differential Constellation Trace Figure (DCTF).

Anomaly detection in wireless communications is a critical issue across a wide range of systems and applications, involving the identification of deviations from normal operation. This concept is particularly significant in the context of radio communications, where anomaly detection plays a vital role in enhancing the overall Quality of Service (QoS) in high density large scale cellular networks. Anomalies can manifest in several forms, such as unauthorized radio transmissions within licensed frequency bands, abrupt changes in propagation conditions within a specific frequency band, or the deliberate interference of communication channels through malicious radio traffic. Recognizing and addressing these anomalies is essential for maintaining the integrity and efficiency of radio communications, ensuring secure and reliable service across the network.

Anomaly detection in the radio spectrum, leveraging Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms, encounters significant challenges: the diversity of anomalies complicates the creation of comprehensive datasets, leading to a preference for unsupervised or semi-supervised learning due to the difficulty in obtaining labelled data related to all anomaly conditions. Additionally, the rarity of anomalies results in uneven dataset distributions, with a predominance of normal traffic samples that can lower the detection performance. To overcome this, the common approach is the use of Adversarial Auto-Encoder networks (AAE) [11]. In this approach, an AAE network is trained to rebuild a signal from pre-processed features, based on clean, non-anomaly radio transmissions. This approach was presented by Rajendran et al. in [12], their results showing that the proposed model has high level of performances in detecting anomalies characterized by the presence of unusual signals within the frequency band being analyzed. However, the

Fig. 2. Spectrum Sensing AI framework for B5G technologies.

anomalies that closely resemble the original signal, such as the overlay of a narrowband radio transmission on an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) transmission, are hard to detect, particularly at both low and high SNR levels.

Tandiya et al. introduce a distinctive method for anomaly detection in the radio spectrum using predictive networks, specifically focusing on the Prednet [13] network, as outlined in [14]. Prednet is designed to predict an upcoming frame based on a sequence of preceding frames. Their approach involves training the Prednet network in sequences of normal radio traffic. Anomalies are identified by comparing the frame predicted by Prednet against the actual frame obtained from radio spectrum analysis. This comparison hinges on the principle that deviations in the predicted versus actual frames indicate the presence of anomalies. Inputs for this process include sequences of plots derived from Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) or sequences of cyclostationary features.

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In this section, we have discussed in detail the main challenges related to spectrum sensing techniques and the immense potential they bring to wireless communications. The methods were mainly divided into likelihood-based probabilistic approaches, AI feature-based approaches and anomaly detection based on unsupervised training. We can conclude that there is a gap in the scientific literature related to how these spectrum sensing techniques can improve B5G communications and pave the way for future 6G network architectures.

III. SPECTRUM SENSING FOR B5G COMMUNICATIONS

Compared to previous generations of technology, the introduction of 5G communications has significantly improved mobile and cellular technologies. It uses sub-1 GHz bands for wider coverage and deep indoor penetration, mid-band frequencies for a balance of coverage and capacity, and high-band (millimetre wave) frequencies for ultra-high data rates in dense urban areas.

Using massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) [15] and beamforming to increase spectral efficiency and network capacity, 5G communications will support a variety of new use cases, including enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC) for critical applications such as autonomous vehicles and remote surgery, and massive machine-to-machine communications (mMTC) for the Internet of Things (IoT) with billions of connected devices. All these enhancements need radio channel agility in order to increase the performance level. This radio channel resource flexibility enables the network to dynamically adapt to the varying traffic demands and service requirements, ensuring a consistent and high-quality user experience.

The development of Beyond 5G (B5G) technologies as the next evolution of mobile communication protocols will offer even higher data rates, increased bandwidths and a shift to higher frequencies. Given the characteristics of 5G and B5G communications, the need for spectrum sensing algorithms cannot be neglected. Leveraging machine learning and artificial intelligence can enhance spectrum sensing by enabling

predictive analytics and more intelligent decision-making. AI can help predict spectrum availability, identify patterns of interference, and optimize spectrum usage dynamically.

The attributes of 5G also include its extensive coverage, enhanced angular and temporal resolution capabilities, a high probability of line-of-sight (LOS) communication conditions, and high data rates, ensuring minimal latency. 5G New Radio (NR) technology differentiates itself from previous cellular technologies, like Long-Term Evolution (LTE), through its array of features that align well with radar system development. A key advantage of 5G NR is its support for millimeter-wave frequencies, which facilitates the utilization of wideband communication channels of up to 400 MHz. The 5G main frequency bands include the low-band (Sub-1 GHz, 600 MHz to 1 GHz), Mid-Band (1 GHz to 6 GHz) and High-Band (Millimeter Wave, 24 GHz and above) [16].

5G NR radar technology is primarily centered around two methodologies. The first method leverages downlink (DL) transmissions, utilizing signals emitted by the base station (referred to as gNB in 3GPP standards) to create environmental maps. This approach enables the gNB to detect and analyze reflections from its DL transmissions. Alternatively, it can process reflections from the DL transmissions of other gNBs, functioning like a passive radar system. The second method employs uplink (UL) signals originating from user equipment (UE), offering a different approach for radar detection and environmental mapping. While B5G communications are designed to be aware of the radio spectrum, within the Smart City framework, numerous Internet of Things (IoT) protocols exist for low-rate data transmission, low power consumption, and rapid deployment without any built-in spectrum awareness mechanisms.

In such high density large scale scenarios, optimizing the radio spectrum can be achieved through spectrum sensing techniques, which have increasingly relied on Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms designed for efficiency [17]. However, the computational demands of ML/DL are high, potentially limiting network scalability in terms of implementation costs if deployed at the sensor level for spectrum sensing.

In this context, B5G communications like 6G offer a solution by facilitating the transmission of data collected by spectrum sensing to cloud centers (situated at the edge of the B5G architecture) equipped to handle the computational load of ML and DL algorithms. This approach leverages the low latency and high data rates of B5G networks to ensure efficient data transfer from multiple sensors to the cloud. It enables the application of Joint and Cooperative Spectrum Sensing techniques based on ML and DL algorithms at the cloud level, optimizing the radio spectrum for low power wireless sensor networks within the smart and sustainable city framework.

Fig. 2 presents an overview of the Spectrum Sensing (SS) entity deployment that can be integrated as an AI orchestrator for radio channel resource optimization in B5G networks of the future. The architecture's foundation is based on Software-Defined Radio (SDR) devices, which are essential for the capture of radio signals. Subsequently, these signals are processed through an Artificial Intelligence (AI) models

dedicated to identifying unused frequency channels. Given that the foundation of the proposed Spectrum Sensing architecture is the AI model, the focus of the SS entity's development and implementation is aligned with the training and evaluation of this AI model:

The AI algorithms can also provide advanced analytics to telecom network operators, determine the list of free channels that will allow for channel allocation with reduced interference, determine the channels occupation percentage, and even allow communication technology identification. These AI algorithms will run on the core network of B5G architecture and enhance the future communication networks. In the European project Hexa-X H2020-ICT-2020-2 [18] final report the word "trustworthiness" appears approx. 80 times. The solution to the trustworthiness of B5G networks is represented by AI algorithms. Spectrum Sensing advanced AI algorithms can improve the stability of the systems and increase the scalability of future B5G networks.

IV. SPECTRUM SENSING INTEGRATION

In this section we present the framework for B5G spectrum sensing that includes spectrum capture and labelling of the signals, training a CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) neural network for waveform classification and finally using the trained AI architecture in test environment for performance evaluation and AI inference .

As previously presented the first challenge was related to the development of a comprehensive dataset for the training /validation and evaluation of the AI model, This designed dataset contains NR 5G signals, generated utilizing specialized software compliant with 5G standards. This approach guarantees the reliability and authenticity of the dataset, thereby enhancing the robustness and efficacy of the AI model's training and evaluative processes ensuring generalization of the developed architecture.

The second step is related to dataset cleaning, preprocessing and feature elimination: The process of dataset cleaning, preprocessing, and feature elimination employs techniques such as signal processing, data augmentation, and feature elimination to further refine the dataset. This phase is dedicated to augmenting the dataset's quality, with the ultimate goal of enhancing the AI model's efficiency and accuracy. By applying these methodologies, this activity focuses on generating discriminative features within the captured data, thereby ensuring that the AI model can effectively identify the used/unused frequency channels in NR 5G radio spectrum.

The third step of the developed framework included design and testing of multiple AI models like including Machine Learning (ML) models, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for image classification, and Deep Learning frameworks for Object Detection. These AI models along with several other novel AI models will undergo evaluation, utilizing both validation and testing datasets in addition to live deployment scenarios. The assessment of these models will be done using specific performance metrics, including scatter plots, confusion matrices, Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of their efficacy and precision in real-world applications.

The hardware environment includes a computing unit for AI design environment with Matlab [19] and a Ettus USRP X310 [20] device that is used for spectrum sensing capturing. The classification problem included 4 classes corresponding to the following categories: NR 5G technologies, 4G technologies, noise, and unknown transmission [21].

The AI architecture uses a custom CNN semantic segmentation network with a dimension of 128x128 pixels, built on 23 layers. The neural network is trained on a dataset of 2700 spectrograms containing 900 spectrograms with 4G communication, 900 spectrograms with NR 5G communication and 900 spectrograms containing a mixed setup of 4G and NR 5G. All spectrograms were generated empirically using the Matlab Wireless Waveform Generator toolbox and used in the training process of the spectrum sensing AI algorithm. The dataset was divided into 80% for training, 10% for validation and 10% for testing.

The hardware platform used for deep learning training on a set of 100 epochs with a learning rate of 0.02, drop factor of 0.1 per 10 epochs is an Alienware Aurora R10 system (AMD Ryzen9 3950X, 64GB DDR4, 2xGeForce RTX 3060 6GB). Figure 3 shows the confusion matrix, which achieved an overall mean accuracy of 97.1% on the test dataset when classifying 4G and NR 5G.

Fig. 3. Confusion Matrix for testing.

The next step was to test the trained AI algorithm in a control environment like a semi-anechoic chamber as seen in Fig.4. These tests have been conducted at the Electromagnetic Compatibility Laboratory [22].

The Electromagnetic Compatibility Laboratory (EMCLab) for spectrum sensing measurements in operating conditions without interferences. This laboratory includes a 3m TDK semi-anechoic room providing a fit environment for prototypes EMC experimental analysis. These conditions allow us to test the robustness of the trained algorithm. The test includes the Pluto SDR [23] device that is used to automatically generate waveforms compliant with 4G and NR 5G. The generated signal is received by a URSP X310 device that captures it processes and classifies it using the already trained AI algorithm that runs on a host computer. The test setup is presented in Fig.4.

Fig. 4. Developed testbed setup in the semi-anechoic chamber.

The evaluation of the developed AI algorithm already trained included a live deployment on Orange 4G and 5G communication frequency bands that were available at our WirelessLab [25] premises. Using Orange support the frequency bands presented in Table 1 were analysed in the inference process of the trained AI algorithms.

TABLE I. MONITORED FREQUENCY BANDS

4G Band			
Frequency Band Number	Duplex Mode	Uplink (MHz)	DownLink (MHz)
3	FDD ^a	1710 – 1785	1805 – 1880
7	FDD	2500 – 2570	2620 – 2690
5G Band			
N1	FDD	1920 – 1980	2110 – 2170
N78	TDD ^b	3550 – 3700	

^a. FDD- Frequency Division Duplexing.

^b. TDD- Time Division Duplexing.

Fig. 5 shows the results of the trained algorithm in the live deployment test. The live deployment test involves the identification of real mobile network communications in a real operational environment. We can see that the classified spectrogram below are correctly classified as 5G when scanning the frequency bands N1 and N78. As can be seen, 4G communications are correctly classified in frequency bands 3 and 7. The problem arises for the uplink channel in 4G, which is classified as 5G by the AI algorithm. This anomaly is due to the similarity of the 4G uplink signals to the 5G uplink signals in a real operating environment where multiple transmissions are taking place simultaneously.

Fig. 5. Test results in real operating environment of the developed AI algorithm.

V. CONCLUSIONS

By employing spectrum sensing techniques, the detection and utilization of available frequency bands can significantly enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of B5G communication systems in congested spectrum environments. Also, the detection and identification of radio transmissions can aid in creating spectrum usage patterns that can be used by the telecom network operators to schedule and relocate radio in order to decrease the congestion, interference, and increase network scalability. Therefore, the integration of spectrum sensing mechanisms becomes increasingly crucial in addressing the challenges posed by spectrum overcrowding and optimizing overall future B5G communication systems performance. From the obtained results we can conclude that the developed AI algorithm ensures a high level of performance achieving an accuracy of 97,1% when classifying 4G and NR 5G waveforms.

Future work will include further validation and testing of the trained AI algorithm in real operating conditions. Performance

metrics will be recorded and analysed in real time. Also, the training process will use live radio captures.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was funded by the European Commission under the European Union's Horizon Europe program – grant agreement No. 101139176 (6G-MUSICAL project) and grant agreement No. 101139291 (iSEE-6G project). The paper solely reflects the views of the authors. The Commission is not responsible for the contents of this paper or any use made thereof.

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